

Nursery Education in Schools, Significance for Career

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Abstract

Nursery education in schools plays key roles for medical practice in nurse career. To promote medical and technical work, different nursery training systems and multi-disciplinary medicines are introduced and discussed-including which character and quality is most important for students in nursery schools. This article addresses nursery training systems and disciplines that students may learn from and benefit for whole life.

Keywords

Healthcare; Nursing; Medical Service; Modern Technology; Education; Personalized Medicine; Obesity; Psycho-Analysis

Introduction

Medical care and nursing advances greatly improve patient's recovery and disease controls in the clinic. The medical significance of the quality promotion of nursing activity and satisfactory is notable [1-7]. This editorial addresses this interesting topic from new insights.

Methods

The key for nursery study and practice is the nurse quality buildup; it includes different and important quality of Responsibility, Cooperative ability, Communication skills, Carefulness, Literary skills, Insist braveness (not always a good thing) and others [8-11].

These qualities should be translated into academic performance, levels and grades of nursery students in the nursery schools. These different qualities should be well represented in their college grades and useful for the hospitals that may choose nurses in the future.

Results

Through quality buildup, the nurses can enter into the hospitals and familiar with work in different departments (Table 1) shows category of nurses in general discipline [12-15]. Nurses can integrate these two spectrums of medical knowledge and finally into their nursery careers (Table 1).

Currently, different medications are gearing up in more global hospitals. It is very difficult to teach all types of medical information for nurses. Medical knowledge is not at the top of nursery training for economic consideration.

Discussion

Major medical knowledge training in nurse career should be a future trend; including medical information of different disease categories and therapeutic disciplines. Through these medical training, nurses may be more happy in their work and update their quality obviously.

Major disciplines	Technical catalog	Requirements
Surgery and anesthesia	Local or whole-body	Individual conditions
Psychiatric	Cognitive, behavior and emotional	Suicidal risk and custody
Emergency	Blood, respiratory and life indicates	Testing and support
Pharmacology	Efficacy and toxicity monitors	Careful observation
Nursery	Different medical disciplines	Physical and spiritual
Patient condition	Gender and ages	Emphasize for categories

Table 1: Medical service by entering into hospitals

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Emergency medication [16,17], Viral infection and treatments [18,19], Mental diseases [20-22], Bone disorders [23-24], Metabolic diseases (type 2 diabetes and obesity) [25-33], Cancer metastasis treatments [34-38], Multi-targeted drugs and herbal medicine [39,40], Personalized (precision) medicine [41-45], Palliative treatments [46-48].

After all, nurses should be familiar with all these knowledge of medical disciplines and execute their service in high quality. Nursery school should carefully teach, organize and monitor student learning. They can even organize students to go abroad and learn medical systems of other countries [11]. After these abroad experiences, nurse students may find jobs of other countries.

Conclusion

Nursery services in the hospitals are affected by nurse education and training. Many work and organization need to promote. Overall, nursery training should be more emphasized at different stages [49]. Many new nursery training systems can be built from systematic investigations and study.

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